

KHURSHID DAVRON'S POEMS IN OTHER LANGUAGES

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Literature is the voice of the soul of the nation. (V. Hugo) He explores the inner world of the nation. Khurshid Davron's work, who is a connoisseur of literature and has a place in the heart of the nation, has a special place not only in Uzbek literature, but also internationally. because his poems were translated into other languages and widely published.

Translation is a reliable tool in the exchange of information, science, technology, and cultural works, which is constantly increasing. Translation is considered to be a powerful factor of establishing communication between peoples of the whole world, first of all brotherly peoples in regular cooperation, a link connecting separate national cultures, a tool that accelerates the development of languages and regulates and stabilizes scientific and technical terminology.

One of the most important issues is to learn whether the creative works that are the product of our literature are translated into other languages in the original, correct and without any changes, and its influence and feelings do not change during the translation. We will consider this based on Khurshid Davron's work.

КУЗ СУРАТИ

Яна сокин чорбоғлар аро
Ёмғир ёғар шитир-шитирлаб,
Яна менинг кулоғимга ғам
Ниманидир айтар шивирлаб.
Яна тиниқ тортар ўйларим,
Худди қамиш шовиллашидек,
Яна дилда жўшдар куйларим,
Хазонларнинг ловиллашидек.
Қора тортган дала сўнгида
Зўрға босиб бужур титроғин,

Қари чинор дуолар ўқиб

Кўмаётир сўнгги япроғин...

Each season has its own beauty, gives people a special pleasure when it comes to dowry. Pleasure gives people peace, inspiration for poets, sustenance for working people, and its beauty for people of knowledge. Khurshid Davron was inspired by this pleasure. In his poem "Autumn Picture" describing the processes of the autumn season, the human life is fleeting and the carelessness of time. describes the passage of time. If the human body who reads the poem once admires the skill of the poet, once again remembers the past life path.

The translators who translate the poems of such a skilled poet into another language must be clever and understand the true essence of the poem. That's why they do the work of transferring the soul from one body to another. it is also their responsibility to preserve distracting emotions. A translator who has done this work and feels the mental state of the writer is a skilled translator.

Khurshid Davran's poetry may have seen the world through the hands of such ambassadors.

LE CRI LE PLUS FORT

Le silence le plus fort
est celui de la mouette.

Pourtant avec quelle force hurlent

Les pierres tombales ...

Le silence le plus fort
n'est ni celui des yeux

Ni celui des mouettes, ni celui des pierres.

Le silence le plus fort

est celui des poètes changés en mouettes.

IN TAJIKISTAN

Ёди ширине дарамро куфт,

Дардро шуд сина пойандоз.

Чашми ман оинаро мечуст,

То ки бинад дарди худро боз.

Дар нигоҳам як алам: «Оё»
Имшаб ӯ шамъи ягон хонаст?»
...Акси ман хандид бар ман талх,
Баъд аз ин оинаро бишкаст.

In short, translation is a factor that has an incomparable influence on the development of not only national literature, but also national thinking. Someone was a thousand times right when he said that translation is one of the weapons of national defense. Any work in world literature becomes national property only when translated. Until then, the text, which was "foreign" after translation, starts to "work" for our language and culture. (Khurshid Davron) Khurshid Davron's poems may have become a bullet for one of these weapons of national defense.

USED LITERATURE

1. "THE POETIC STYLE OF KHURSHID DAVRON". *science Journal "NovaInfo"* (Vol.1, No. 72).
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3. **Action Poétique N°115.1989, U.R.S.S. POÈTES OUZBEKS ET RUSSES**
4. Khurshid Davron “Qadrdon quyosh” Toshkent .1979.